

Examples of Modification of Equations of Mathematical Physics

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Abstract

In [1], [2], [3] a mathematical construction was presented that describes the dynamical change of the dimension of a multilinear space of objects of tensor nature. A change of dimension leads to a change in the cardinality of the set of objects. This space, which accounts for the change of cardinality, differs radically from the representation of a collection of objects of smaller cardinality as a subspace of a space of maximal and constant dimension. This approach leads to a modification of integro-differential expressions. In the present work some equations of mathematical physics are investigated under conditions of variable dimension. It is shown that taking into account the presence of a variable dimension under conditions of constant dimension does not alter the physical predictions (the Feynman integral) or the form of the equations (the Dirac equation, Maxwell's equations). However, when the dimension varies, all the indicated equations acquire physically significant additional terms.

1 Introduction

In [1], [2], [3] a mathematical construction was presented that describes the dynamical change of the dimension of a multilinear space of objects of tensor nature. A change of dimension leads to a change in the cardinality of the set of objects. This space, which accounts for the change of cardinality, differs radically from the representation of a collection of objects of smaller cardinality as a subspace of a space of maximal and constant dimension. This approach leads to a modification of integro-differential expressions.

We investigate some equations of mathematical physics under conditions of variable dimension. The exposition relies on classical results of quantum field theory [4,5] and the theory of partial differential equations [6].

2 Modification of the Lagrangian of quantum electrodynamics

The standard Lagrangian of quantum electrodynamics has the form [4]:

$$\mathcal{L} = \bar{\psi} (i\gamma^\mu \partial_\mu - m) \psi - \frac{1}{4} F_{\mu\nu} F^{\mu\nu} - e \bar{\psi} \gamma^\mu \psi A_\mu \quad (1)$$

where ψ is the electron-positron field, A_μ is the photon field. The system of units $\hbar = c = 1$ is adopted, and the expression itself is written in covariant form.

Let us perform the dimensional modification of the constituent parts of the Lagrangian \mathcal{L} :

$$(i\gamma^\mu \partial_\mu - m) \psi = i\gamma^\mu \partial_\mu \psi - m\psi$$

$$\begin{aligned} i\gamma^\mu \partial_\mu \psi - m\psi &\longrightarrow i\gamma^\mu M \partial_\mu (\psi M) - m\psi M = \\ &= i\gamma^\mu M M \partial_\mu \psi + i\gamma^\mu M \psi \partial_\mu M - m\psi M = \\ &= i\gamma^\mu M \partial_\mu \psi + i\gamma^\mu M \psi \partial_\mu |\omega| - m\psi M = \\ &= (i\gamma^\mu M \partial_\mu + i\gamma^\mu M \partial_\mu |\omega| - mM) \psi = \\ &= M(i\gamma^\mu \partial_\mu + i\gamma^\mu \partial_\mu |\omega| - m) \psi \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\psi} (i\gamma^\mu \partial_\mu - m) \psi &\longrightarrow \bar{\psi} M M (i\gamma^\mu \partial_\mu + i\gamma^\mu \partial_\mu |\omega| - m) \psi = \\ &= M \bar{\psi} (i\gamma^\mu \partial_\mu + i\gamma^\mu \partial_\mu |\omega| - m) \psi \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

This term represents the creation and annihilation of particles of the electron-positron field.

Continuing:

$$\frac{1}{4} F_{\mu\nu} F^{\mu\nu} \longrightarrow \frac{1}{4} F_{\mu\nu} M F^{\mu\nu} M = \frac{1}{4} F_{\mu\nu} F^{\mu\nu} M \quad (3)$$

According to [3], $M_{int} = \text{const}$. This term accounts for the electromagnetic field.

$$e\bar{\psi} \gamma^\mu \psi A_\mu \longrightarrow e\bar{\psi} M \gamma^\mu M \psi M A_\mu M = e\bar{\psi} \gamma^\mu \psi A_\mu M \quad (4)$$

which gives a description of the interaction of electrons, positrons, and photons.

Substituting (2), (3), (4) into (1):

$$\mathcal{L} \longrightarrow \bar{\psi} (i\gamma^\mu \partial_\mu + i\gamma^\mu \partial_\mu |\omega| - m) \psi M - \frac{1}{4} F_{\mu\nu} F^{\mu\nu} M - e\bar{\psi} \gamma^\mu \psi A_\mu M = M \tilde{\mathcal{L}} \quad (5)$$

The Lorentz gauge condition takes the following form [5]:

$$\partial_\mu A^\mu = 0 \longrightarrow \partial_\mu (A^\mu M) = M \partial_\mu A^\mu + A^\mu \partial_\mu M = 0 \quad (6)$$

3 Modification of the Feynman integral

Let q' and q'' be two quantum states between which a transition $q' \longrightarrow q''$ takes place. The representation of the transition amplitude in the form of a Feynman path integral has the form [7]:

$$\langle q'' | u(t'' - t') | q' \rangle = \frac{1}{N} \int D_q \left(\exp \left(-\frac{i}{\hbar} \int_{t'}^{t''} \mathcal{L} dt \right) \right) \quad (7)$$

where $D_q = \Pi_i dq_i(t)$.

Substituting (5) into (7):

$$\begin{aligned} &\langle q'' | u(t'' - t') | q' \rangle = \\ &= \frac{1}{N} \int D_q \left(\exp \left(-\frac{i}{\hbar} M \int_{t'}^{t''} \left(\bar{\psi} (i\gamma^\mu \partial_\mu + i\gamma^\mu \partial_\mu |\omega| - m) \psi - \frac{1}{4} F_{\mu\nu} F^{\mu\nu} - ie\bar{\psi} \gamma^\mu \psi A_\mu \right) dt \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{1}{N} \int D_q \left(\exp \left(-\frac{i}{\hbar} M \left\{ \int \mathcal{L} dt + \int_{t'}^{t''} i\bar{\psi} \gamma^\mu \partial_\mu |\omega| \psi dt \right\} \right) \right) \quad (8)$$

If $M = \text{const}$, then $\partial_\mu |\omega| = 0$ and

$$\langle q'' | u(t'' - t') | q' \rangle = \frac{1}{N} \int D_q \exp \left(-\frac{i}{\hbar} M \int_{t'}^{t''} \mathcal{L} dt \right)$$

The action $S(t'', t') = \int_{t'}^{t''} \mathcal{L} dt$; thus, under conditions of unchanged dimension, the very accounting for the dimension yields:

$$S \longrightarrow M \cdot S, \text{ where } M = \text{const}$$

Multiplication of the action by a constant (just as an additive term) does not alter physical predictions, which guarantees the independence of the quantum theory from the choice of the zero point of the action. The Lorentz gauge condition is preserved (see (6)).

Thus, the mathematical accounting for the presence of a factor of possible change of dimension under conditions of constant dimension does not affect the transition amplitudes between quantum states of the system.

If, however, $M \neq \text{const}$, at points of a set of measure greater than 0 [3], the action S acquires a dependence of the form (8) on $\partial_\mu |\omega|$, which is transferred to the probability amplitude of the transition $q' \rightarrow q''$.

4 Modification of the Dirac equation

Let us separately write out the Dirac equation [4,5]:

$$(i\gamma^\mu D_\mu - m) \psi = i\gamma^\mu D_\mu \psi - m\psi$$

$$D_\mu = \partial_\mu - ieA_\mu$$

We perform the dimensional modification:

$$\begin{aligned} i\gamma^\mu \partial_\mu \psi - e\gamma^\mu A_\mu \psi - m\psi &\longrightarrow i\gamma^\mu M \partial_\mu (\psi M) - e\gamma^\mu M A_\mu M \psi M - m\psi M = \\ &= i\gamma^\mu M M \partial_\mu \psi + i\gamma^\mu M \psi \partial_\mu M - e\gamma^\mu M A_\mu M \psi M - m\psi M = \\ &= (i\gamma^\mu M \partial_\mu + i\gamma^\mu M \partial_\mu M - e\gamma^\mu A_\mu M - mM) \psi = \\ &= M (i\gamma^\mu \partial_\mu + i\gamma^\mu \partial_\mu M - e\gamma^\mu A_\mu - m) \psi = \\ &= M (i\gamma^\mu D_\mu - m) \psi + M i\gamma^\mu \partial_\mu M \psi \\ &= M (i\gamma^\mu D_\mu - m) \psi + M i\gamma^\mu \partial_\mu M \psi \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Correspondingly, for $M = \text{const}$, $\partial_\mu M = 0$:

$$(i\gamma^\mu D_\mu - m) \psi = 0 \longrightarrow M (i\gamma^\mu D_\mu - m) \psi = 0, \quad M = \text{const}$$

$$(i\gamma^\mu D_\mu - m) \psi = 0$$

Thus, accounting for the dimension under the condition $M = \text{const}$ does not lead to a physically significant change of the Dirac equation. If, however, $M \neq \text{const}$ under the conditions according to [3], the Dirac equation is modified into the form (9).

5 Modification of Maxwell's equations

Finally, consider Maxwell's equations in covariant form [5]:

$$\partial_\mu F^{\mu\nu} = e\bar{\psi}\gamma^\nu\psi$$

where $F^{\mu\nu} = \partial^\mu A^\nu - \partial^\nu A^\mu$ is the electromagnetic field tensor, $j^\nu = e\bar{\psi}\gamma^\nu\psi$ is the 4-current.

We perform the transition:

$$\longrightarrow \partial_\mu (F^{\mu\nu} M) = e\bar{\psi}M\gamma^\nu M\psi M$$

$$M\partial_\mu F^{\mu\nu} + F^{\mu\nu}\partial_\mu M = e\bar{\psi}\gamma^\nu\psi M$$

If $\partial_\mu M = M\partial_\mu|\omega|$, then:

$$M\partial_\mu F^{\mu\nu} + F^{\mu\nu}M\partial_\mu|\omega| = e\bar{\psi}\gamma^\nu\psi M$$

The factor M again cancels:

$$\partial_\mu F^{\mu\nu} = e\bar{\psi}\gamma^\nu\psi - F^{\mu\nu}\partial_\mu|\omega| \quad (10)$$

For $M = \text{const}$, $\partial_\mu|\omega| = 0$, Maxwell's equations turn out to be unchanged. However, under the condition $M \neq \text{const}$ (in the sense of [3]) they take the form (10). The resulting modification of Maxwell's equations can be compared with approaches developed in theories with broken Lorentz invariance [8].

6 Conclusion

Thus, accounting for the presence of a variable dimension, according to the algebraic construction developed in [1], [2], [3], under conditions of constant dimension does not alter the physical predictions, as in the case of the Feynman integral, or does not in principle change the form of the equations (the Dirac equation, Maxwell's equations in covariant form). However, when the dimension varies in a definite manner, all the indicated equations acquire physically significant additional terms. The regularities that hold in constant-dimension sections are completely unchanged, while the space of variable dimension as a whole is non-Riemannian, owing to which the additional effects that arise in regions of non-Riemannian transitions are, generally speaking, expected and subject to investigation.

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